

Local Government in Italy

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Italy	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Italy: An Introduction	5
2.2. <i>Public-Private Partnerships and Social Housing</i>	7
2.3. <i>Bridging the Urban-Rural Digital Divide</i>	11
2.4. <i>Strategic Planning in Geographically Heterogeneous Metropolises</i>	18
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Italy: An Introduction.....	24
3.2. <i>Investment Spending of Local Entities</i>	28
3.3. <i>The Revision of the Inter-Municipal Equalization Mechanism in Trentino</i>	31
3.4. <i>Financial Assistance to Municipalities with Structural Deficits</i>	36
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Italy: An Introduction	42
4.2. <i>Unions of Municipalities in Emilia-Romagna</i>	50
4.3. <i>Mergers of Municipalities – A Comparison of Procedures and Their Implications</i>	54
4.4. <i>The Valley Communities (comunità di valle) in the Province of Trento</i>	59
4.5. <i>Inter-municipal Cooperation Based on a Model Agreement: A Top-Down Approach in South Tyrol</i>	63
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Italy: An Introduction.....	71
5.2. <i>The Inclusion of Local Governments in Italy’s Multilevel Conference System of Intergovernmental Relations</i>	74
5.3. <i>The Council of Municipalities of South Tyrol as Facilitator of Local-Subnational Relations</i>	79
5.4. <i>Migration Management as an Intergovernmental Cooperation Instrument in Rural Areas</i>	83
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in Italy: An Introduction	91
6.2. <i>Participatory Budgeting in Italy: The Case of the Municipality of Mals</i>	94
6.3. <i>District Laboratories (‘laboratori di quartiere’) in the City of Bologna</i>	99
6.4. <i>Regulations on Common Goods</i>	103

Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments

5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Italy: An Introduction

Greta Klotz, *Eurac Research*

When it comes to intergovernmental relations with the national government, local government associations are the main actors. The National Association of Italian Municipalities (*Associazione dei Comuni Italiani – ANCI*) has a long-established tradition, as it was founded in 1901 as a non-profit organization active throughout the national territory. It is not recognized by the Italian Constitution, but as the main representative organization of local authorities, it is institutionally anchored in the system of the multilateral cooperation mechanisms with the national government. Not all Italian municipalities are members of the ANCI. As of July 2019, it had 7,041 members from among 7,914 Italian municipalities and represents approx. 90 per cent of the Italian population.¹⁴² The main goal of ANCI is to represent the interests of municipalities and metropolitan cities vis-à-vis the national and regional governments. It is also a facilitator of international cooperation and even a shareholder of some companies for service provision.

ANCI's assembly, bringing together all members, meets once a year, but the organization has 17 permanent commissions on different policy fields, ranging from local finances and social welfare to immigration and integration policies. Furthermore, ANCI comprises within its structure several special interest bodies. Among others, there is a National Council of Small Municipalities (*Consulta Nazionale dei Piccoli Comuni*). This institution represents all ANCI municipalities with a population of less than 5,000 inhabitants and has the aim to secure and promote the coordination of initiatives, which support small municipalities and to promote initiatives with regard to inter-municipal cooperation. Apart from this council, there is within ANCI also a Coordination Body of Metropolitan Cities' (*Coordinamento delle Città Metropolitane*). Similar to the aim of the above-mentioned council, the task of this coordination body is to support specific initiatives with regard to the metropolitan realities. The mayors of the 14 metropolitan cities as well as the coordinator of the Council of Small Municipalities, also the coordinators of regional councils of small municipalities, are members of the important National Council (*Consiglio nazionale*) of ANCI. This body is important because it determines above all the strategic direction of the association. As in addition to the mayors of the metropolitan cities those of all regional and provincial capitals participate as well, there seems to be a certain imbalance of representation in favor of urban areas.

¹⁴² National Institute of Statistics, 'Codici statistici delle unità amministrative territoriali, novità per l'anno 2019' (*Istat*, 30 June 2019) <<https://www.istat.it/it/archivio/6789>>.

ANCI is complemented by the National Association of the Italian Provinces (*Unione delle Province d'Italia* – UPI) as well as the National Union of Mountain Towns and Communities (*Unione Nazionale Comuni, Comunità ed Enti Montani* – UNCCEM).

In terms of local government councils at the regional level, it should be pointed out that ANCI has branches in all of the 20 Italian regions. In the Autonomous Provinces of Bolzano and Trento, the ANCI is represented by particular provincial associations of local authorities, i.e. the *Consorzio dei Comuni della Provincia di Bolzano-Südtiroler Gemeindenverband* and the *Consorzio dei Comuni della Provincia di Trento*.

Apart from the regional branches of ANCI, an important body of intergovernmental relations between the regions and local entities was established by the constitutional reform in 2001. According to Article 123 of the Italian Constitution, regions with ordinary statute have to foresee and regulate in their statute a so-called Council of Local Authorities (*Consiglio delle Autonomie Locali* – CAL), an organ ensuring consultation between regions and local authorities. All 20 regions have established this institution. Although the five regions with special statute (Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Sardinia, Sicily, Trentino-South Tyrol and Val d'Aosta) enjoy autonomous competences regarding the organization and functioning of local authorities and are, following the Constitutional Court decision no 370/2006, not obliged to establish this institution, all of them have also set up such an advisory body. The main task of a CAL is consultation and sometimes their advice during the legislative process is compulsory. The councils of local authorities of some regions established in 2012 a Permanent Coordination Body of CALs in order to promote inter-regional collaboration between these institutions, as well as to exchange experiences and best practices among each other. According to a recent study, the CALs in the regions with ordinary statute have so far only played a marginal role of influence in regional decision-making, with the lacking implementation of the principle of subsidiarity being a main reason.¹⁴³

As for mechanisms of supervision, it is important to note that the constitutional reform in 2001 cancelled Article 130 of the Constitution, which had foreseen, according to the principle of hierarchy between levels of government, a regional preventive control of acts of local authorities. Before this change the regions had tightly controlled the provinces and municipalities and had been controlled, in turn, by the national government. However, there is still a system of internal administrative monitoring, auditing and the extraordinary substitution power under Article 120 of the Constitution.

According to this provision, '[t]he Government can act for bodies of the regions, metropolitan cities, provinces and municipalities if the latter fail to comply with international rules and treaties or EU legislation, or in the case of grave danger for public safety and security, or whenever such action is necessary to preserve legal or economic unity and in particular to

¹⁴³ Elena di Carpegna Brivio, 'Il CAL tra sogno e realtà. Problemi attuali delle istituzioni di raccordo nel sistema regionale delle fonti' (2018) 5 *Federalismi.it* <<http://www.consigliautonomieitaliane.it/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/Inserire.pdf>>.

guarantee the basic level of benefits relating to civil and social entitlements, regardless of the geographic borders of local authorities. The law shall lay down the procedures to ensure that subsidiary powers are exercised in compliance with the principles of subsidiarity and loyal co-operation'. This power of the national government to intervene is only for the exceptional circumstances explicitly mentioned in the cited provision and measures must observe the principle of proportionality. Only those measures may be taken that are necessary to achieve, to the benefit of citizens, a swift return to normality and legality. Financial supervision is exercised by the Court of Auditors and its regional branches. Law no 131/2003 strengthened control powers of these courts. But this supervision does not concern the political assessment of measures taken by local governments. It controls the compliance of local government actions with budget legislation and other rules and policies from the regional, national and EU levels, especially regarding financial mismanagement and balanced budget requirements.

The most important mechanisms for intergovernmental cooperation between the national government, regions and local authorities are the following two conferences: the Conference of the State, Cities and Local Autonomies (hereinafter CSCLA) and the Unified Conference, which brings together the CSCLA with the Conference of the State, Regions and Autonomous Provinces. The latter conference therefore comprises three levels of government (national, subnational and local). The CSCLA was introduced with the Decree of the President of the Council of Ministers on 2 July 1996 and was reformed by the Legislative Decree no 281/1997. The same legislative decree also created the Unified Conference.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

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